

CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE AND COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENTS OF VASCULAR AND ALZHEIMER'S ORIGIN

Valkova M.

MD, PhD

University Hospital "Sofamed", Sofia, Bulgaria

Abstract

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is frequent among elderly patients with dementia. The aim of our study was to examine cognitive functions of patients with COPD in cases with Alzheimer's disease (AD), vascular dementia (VD) and mixed dementia (MD) and to compare them to those without COPD.

Material and methods: We examined 48 patients with mild COPD (on average 77.43 ± 7.87 years old; 21 males, 27 females, 8 with AD, 15 with VD and 25 with MD) and 98 patients with dementia but without COPD (77.43 ± 7.87 years old, 27 males and 71 females; 30 with AD, 31 with VD and 27 with MD) at two step model (interval of 2 years) with the following neuropsychological battery: Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), Isaac's Set Test (IST), Literal fluency Test (LFT), Clock Drawing Test, 10 Words Test, Digit Symbol Substitution test (DSST), Digit Span Test (DST).

Results: Patients with COPD showed more pronounced decreases on global cognitive function (MMSE), LFT, IST, short-term memory and allocable attention vs those without. We failed to find any cognitive differences between patients with and without COPD at AD group. Patients with COPD and VD had low results on IST, LFT, working memory, delayed recall and working memory than those with VD but without COPD, they also showed significantly more prominent decline on LFT and Short-term memory. Patients with COPD and MD showed more prominent decline of global cognition (measured by MMSE) than those without COPD. They also had worse results DST forward.

Conclusions: COPD is associated with executive and memory changes and prominent deep white matter dysfunction. Patients with VD and MD and COPD are more vulnerable. It is unclear if COPD leads to COPD – associated cognitive changes or promotes other kinds of dementia.

Keywords: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), Alzheimer's disease, vascular dementia, mixed dementia.

Introduction: The prevalence of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) among elderly is 14-16% (Al Wachami, 2024). COPD is often associated with incident dementia and worsening of cognitive functions (Ranzini, 2020; Tao, 2020; Wang J, 2022; Rosso, 2023). The results of CAIDE study show association between COPD at middle ages and development of dementia 25 years after that, but not direct association between late onset COPD and degenerative dementia (Rusanen, 2013). According to Higbee et al. (2021) there is no causal relationship between Alzheimer's disease (AD) and COPD. Morris and al. (2019) obtained domain specific cognitive differences between patents with AD, with COPD and controls, suggesting that COPD led to different cognitive profile vs classical AD.

COPD is associated also with high risk for vascular dementia (VD) (Lahousse, 2015; Szylińska, 2022). Such patients have high stroke risk and low poststroke prognosis, because of low oxygen supply and high risk for pulmonary and systemic infections.

COPD may impact the brain function by several mechanisms: total and regional brain hypoxia and hypoxemia, particularly at night, associated with impaired night sleep, stimulation of oxidative stress and aseptic neuroinflammation, promotion of extra and intracerebral atherosclerosis, high level of pulmonary and systemic infections and worsening of heart and kidney functions because of whole body hypoxia and hypoxemia (Lahousse, 2015).

The aim of our study was to examine cognitive functions of patients with COPD in cases with AD, VD and mixed dementia (MD) and to compare them to those without COPD.

Material and methods: We examine 48 patients with mild COPD (on average 77.43 ± 7.87 years old; 21 males, 27 females, 8 with AD, 15 with VD and 25 with MD) and 98 patients with dementia but without COPD (77.43 ± 7.87 years old, 27 males and 71 females; 30 with AD, 31 with VD and 27 with MD). The inclusion criteria of the study were 1. Age ≥ 60 years; 2. Confirmed by neuropsychologist cognitive impairment at ≥ 2 cognitive domains; 3. Confirmed on the basis of history, neurological and somatic examination, laboratory data and imaging study diagnosis of AD or SVD or MD; 4. All patients are examined by pulmologist. Patients with COPD should have 0 to 1 stage of pulmonary failure. All patients with pulmonary failure above 1 stage are excluded; 5. All patients with obstructive sleep apnea are excluded; 6. Lack of other neurological diseases such as trauma, brain tumors, neuroinfections, demyelinating diseases or epilepsy; 7. Lack of decompensation of coexisted somatic diseases during the study; 8. Lack of psychiatric diseases, except of mild depression or anxiety; 9. Lack of treatment or usage of benzodiazepines, modafinile acetate, hallucinogens and other psychoactive drugs, except for low dosages of Quetiapine (≤ 50 mg/d), Pregabalin (≤ 150 mg/d), Gabaneural (≤ 600 mg/d), Hydroxyzine (≤ 25 mg/d) or antidepressants; 10. Lack of alcohol abuse or usage of forbidden substances; 11. Signed informed consent.

After clinical interview and confirmation of the diagnosis, the patients were examined via the following neuropsychological battery: Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), Isaac's Set Test (IST for verbal fluency), Literal fluency Test (LFT; variant M-O-H-A in Bulgarian, 1 minute for every letter), Clock Drawing Test (CDT), 10 Words Test (for working memory, delayed recall and recognition (10/20words), Bulgarian

variant), Digit Symbol Substitution test (DSST 90sec), Digit Span Test (DST forward and backward) and 21 Hamilton Depression Scale (HDS). All patients with HDS above 12 points were excluded.

The same neuropsychological battery was used 2 years after the first examination.

The statistical analysis was done via parametric and non-parametric tests as ANOVA, MANOVA, Man-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis test statistics via SPSS 20.0 and Statgraphics 20.0. All results were interpreted at 95% confidential level ($p < 0.05$).

Results:

1. Demographic data.

Patients with COPD are 33% of all patients (see table 1). Our patients with and without COPD were at similar age. Male:female ratio was higher among COPD group (0.78 vs 0.38). Patients with COPD had slightly low formal education than those without.

2. The association between COPD and cognitive decline.

The differences between COPD and no COPD groups are given at table 2. Patients with COPD showed more pronounced decreases on global cognitive function (MMSE), literal and categorical fluency, short-term memory and allocable attention vs those without. We failed to find statistically significant intergroup differences on long-term memory, recognition, working memory, visual-spatial abilities and focused attention.

3. Cognitive differences between patients with and without COPD among patients with AD.

We failed to find any cognitive differences between patients with and without COPD at AD group. However, patients with AD and COPD were relatively few in number ($N=8$).

4. Cognitive differences between patients with and without COPD at VD group.

Patients with COPD and VD had low results on IST, LFT, working memory, delayed recall and working memory than those with VD but without COPD (see table 3). The group with COPD also showed significantly more prominent decline on LFT and Short-term memory during the period of 2 years. We failed to find intergroup differences on global cognition, recognition, attention and visual-spatial abilities (measured by CDT).

5. Associations between COPD and cognitive impairments among patients with MD.

Patients with COPD and MD showed more prominent decline of global cognition (measured by MMSE) than those without COPD (see table 4). They also had worse results on working memory test (DST forward). We failed to find intergroup differences on short and long term memory, information processing speed, visual spatial abilities and attention.

Discussion

COPD is frequent in elderly. About one third of our patients had mild COPD. The prevalence was highest at MD (51.29%), followed by VD (26.79%) and lowest at AD group (21.05%). COPD was 1.59 more frequent among male patients. Our patients with COPD were slightly low educated than those without. The higher male COPD prevalence is due to higher frequency of environmental and professional risk factors and Tabaco usage among men vs women (Al Wachami, 2024). Although our sample was relatively small and specific, we obtained significantly lower prevalence of

COPD among patients with high vs basic formal education. Worldwide, low education level is associated with socio-economic and health problems and low quality of life (Lutter, 2020; Al Wachami, 2024). Moreover, patients with high education had better COPD outcome, lower complications and lower mortality rate than low educated (Lutter, 2020). So patients with basic education can be seen as a target group for the development of COPD associated complications. Among all our patients we found that those with COPD showed more prominent delay on global cognition, short-term memory and attention for a short time of 2 years than those without. Our results support the hypothesis of more prominent cognitive dysfunction and accelerated cognitive decline among patients with COPD vs those without (Wang Y, 2019; Ranzini, 2020; Tao, 2020; Wang J, 2022; Rosso, 2023). The previous studies associate COPD with global cognitive domain and domain specific cognitive impairments, although the more vulnerable cognitive domains differ from studies to studies. Tondo et al. (2018) suggest that the main cognitive impairments associated with COPD are frontal and executive dysfunctions. Morris et al. (2019) have found association between COPD and memory, attention and verbal fluency changes. Rosso et al. (2023) have found more prominent executive and episodic memory dysfunctions. Lahousse et al. (2015) obtained association between COPD and deep small vessel disease changes and development of dysexecutive syndrome firstly. Our data suggests also suggest more prominent changes at executive domain (information processing speed, short-term and working memory and partially attention). It remains unclear if COPD promotes the development and progression of dementia or it leads to different COPD associated dementia itself, which is superimposed over the coexisting other form of dementia (Tondo, 2018; Morris, 2019). Outside the decompensation of COPD, leading to infectious diseases, cor pulmonale or acute cerebral hypoxia, the most probable pathogenetic mechanisms for COPD associated cognitive dysfunctions are chronic hypoxia, hypoxemia, CO₂ deposition, acidosis, changes at brain microcirculation leading to small vessels damage and promotion of neuro-inflammation and neurotransmitter dysbalance, activation of cortisol production and dysfunction of gliadin system (Tondo, 2018; Wang Y, 2019; Ranzini, 2020; Tao, 2020; Wang J, 2022; Rosso, 2023). COPD is a risk factor for worsening of other cognitive risk factors as cardiac dysfunction, atrial fibrillation, high risk for systemic infections and impaired night sleep (Lahousse, 2015; Szylińska, 2022). However, we failed to find association between COPD and worsening of AD, similar to other authors (Higbe, 2021). However, our sample was too little to draw conclusions. Morris et al. (2019) suggest different cognitive phenotype among patients with AD in relation with COPD although remains unclear if COPD really worsens AD associated cognitive decline. Tondo et al. (2018) obtained slightly worsening of executive functions in patients with COPD and AD vs those with "pure AD", but not worsening of global cognition or other additional domain-specific changes. We obtain statistically significant differences among patients with and without COPD among patients with VD. Patients with COPD show low categorical and literal fluency, low short-term memory, delayed recall and working memory, which might be associated with prominent

dysfunction of deep brain white matter and more prominent small vessels disease. It is found that COPD is associated with shrinkage of white matter, development of lacunar strokes, leucoareosis and microbleedings (Lahousse, 2015), leading to deficits of executive functioning and short-term memory (Tondo, 2018; Morris, 2019; Rosso, 2023). Concentrating on memory changes, we find short-term memory dysfunctions and changes at the level of information extraction from memory depo, but not in episodic memory itself, as stated Rosso et al. (2023). So the deficit is mostly because of disconnection but not at the level of hippocampal memory. However, the treatment of COPD might have some positive effect on cognition of patients with VD. And vice versa, the improvement of cognitive functioning might have positive effects on the COPD outcome (Siraj, 2023).

Our patients with MD and COPD showed the rapidest decline in global cognitive functioning and

most prominent working memory deficits. It seems that global cognition is vulnerable to COPD in cases with MD, but not in with AD and VD. We fail to find any data for the impact of COPD among patients with MD at literature. We think that such patients should be target group for more wide studies on the question.

Cognitive dysfunction influences a number of important life aspects of patients with COPD. It can lead to functional dependence, unhealthy life, inappropriate respiration and rehabilitation. The major role for this plays executive dysfunctions and memory changes that lead to lack of self-control, lack of ability of independent taking care of yourself and low quality of life.

Conclusions

COPD is associated with executive and memory changes and prominent deep white matter dysfunction. Patients with VD and MD and COPD are more vulnerable. It is unclear if COPD leads to COPD – associated cognitive changes or promotes other kinds of dementia.

Table 1

Demographic data

	AD	VD	MD	Total	Age (years)	M:F	B:M:H
Lack of COPD	30	31	27	98	77.43±7.87	27:71	7:54:37
COPD	8	15	25	48	77.25±6.62	21:27	5:29:14
				p	>0.05	0.0001	0.0001
Total	38	56	52	146	76.71±7.47	48:98	12:83:51

Legend: AD – Alzheimer's dementia, VD – vascular dementia, MD – mixed dementia; M:F – males:females; B:M:H – with basic, with middle. With high formal education.

Table 2

The difference between COPD and no COPD groups.

Association between COPD and:	Averages or medianas of patients without COPD vs patients with COPD	p=
MMSE 1 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
MMSE 2 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
2 year MMSE decline (p.)	-1.04±2.63 vs -2.02±2.79	0.0405
IST1 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
IST2 (p.)	28.55±8.70 vs 25.42±8.11	0.0384
2 year IST decline (p.)	-1.5 vs -3.0	0.0117*
LFT 1 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
LFT 2 (p.)	20.94±11.40 vs 16.85±9.80	0.0432
2 year LFT decline (p.)	-2.0 vs -4.0	0.0263*
Short-term memory 10WT 1 (average words number from 5 trials)	NA	p>0.05
Short-term memory 10WT 2 (average words number from 5 trials)	4.68±1.62 vs 4.11±1.44	0.0132
2 year Short-term memory 10WT decline (average words number from 5 trials)	-0.2 vs 0.45	0.0434*
DSST 1 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
DSST 2 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
2 year DSST decline (p.)	-2.0 vs -4.0	0.0405*

Legend: MMSE – Mini Mental State Examination, IST – Isaac's Set Test, Short term memory 10WT – Short – term memory 10 words test, DSST – Digit Symbol Substitution Test
*Kruskal-Wallis Test statistics

Table 3

Association between COPD and cognitive impairment among patients with VD.

Association between COPD and:	Medianas of patients without COPD vs patients with COPD	p=
IST1 (p.)	36.0 vs 30.0	0.0178*
IST2 (p.)	35.0 vs 29.0	0.0137*
2 year IST decline (p.)	NA	p>0.05
LFT 1 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
LFT 2 (p.)	28.5 vs 22.0	0.0331*
2 year LFT decline (p.)	0 vs -2	0.0326^
Short-term memory 10WT 1 (average words number from 5 trials)	6.0 vs 5.2	0.0386*
Short-term memory 10WT 2 (average words number from 5 trials)	5.8 vs 5.0	0.0181*
2 year Short-term memory 10WT decline (average words number from 5 trials)	0.2 vs 0.4	0.0413*
10WT DR 1 (number of words)	5.0 vs 4.0	0.0294*
10WT DR 2 (number of words)	4.0 vs 3.0	0.0160*
2 year delay on DR (number of words)	NA	p>0.05
DST forward 1 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
DST forward 2 (p.)	7.0 vs 6.0	0.0099*
2 year DST forward delay (p.)	NA	p>0.05

Legend: IST – Isaac’s Set Test, Short-term memory 10WT – Short-term memory from 10 words test, 10WT DR – delayed recall from 10 words test, DST – Digit Span Test
* Kruskal-Wallis Test Statistics.

Table 4

The associations between COPD and cognitive impairments among patients with MD.

The association between COPD and	Mediana without COPD vs with COPD	p=
MMSE 1 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
MMSE 2 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
2 year MMSE decline (p.)	-1.0 vs -2.0	0.0460*
DST forward 1 (p.)	3.0 vs 4.0	0.0484*
DST forward 2 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
2 year DST forward delay (p.)	NA	p>0.05

Legend: MMSE – Mini Mental State Examination, DST – Digit Span Test; * Kruskal-Wallis.

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